

HARACTERISTICS OF REPERTORY SELECTION IN CULTURAL EVENTS

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Annotation: This article provides detailed information about the reforms in the field of culture in our country, the organization of cultural events, work on the word and its stages, performing activities, repertoire selection, analysis of solo works.

Key words: art, word, performance, stage, choice, system, process, interest, scene, work.

ОСОБЕННОСТИ ВЫБОРА РЕПЕРТОРИЯ НА КУЛЬТУРНЫХ МЕРОПРИЯТИЯХ

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Аннотация: В данной статье представлена подробная информация о реформах в сфере культуры в нашей стране, организации культурных мероприятий, работе над словом и его сценами, исполнительской деятельности, подборе репертуара, анализе сольных произведений.

Ключевые слова: искусство, слово, спектакль, сцена, выбор, система, процесс, интерес, сцена, произведение.

MADANIY TADBIRLARDA REPERTUAR TANLASH HUSUSIYATLARI

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada mamlakatimizdagi madaniyat sohasidagi islohotlar, madaniy tadbirlarni tashkil etish, so'z ustida ishlash va uning bosqichlari, ijrochilik faoliyati, repertuar tanlash, yakka ijro etiladigan asarlar tahlili haqida batafsil ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: teart, so'z, ijro, bosqich, tanlov, sistema, jarayon, qiziqish, manzara, asar.

Over the past period, the Republic of Uzbekistan has adopted a number of normative and legal acts on the development of culture and arts. In particular, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD - 3391 of November 17, 2017 " On measures to further develop the art of the Uzbek national makom", August 26, 2018 Resolution No. PD - 3920 " On measures for innovative development of the arts ", Resolution No. PD-4038 of November 28, 2018 " On approval of the Concept of further development of national culture in the Republic of Uzbekistan", 2019 Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 1019 of December 19, 2019 "On approval of the Program for improving the activities of museums in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2020-2021", November 23, 2019 Resolution of the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 26, 2019 " On approval of the activities of the Erkin Vakhidov Memorial Museum and the Treasury House Museum" Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 630 [1] of May 30, 2019 " On the organization of the activities of the state museum-reserves Sarmishsay", "Shakhrisabz", "Termez" and "Kokand" Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 443 of April 21 [2] , 2020 "On measures to further increase the efficiency of the fine and applied arts" Resolution No. PD - 4688 of May

26, 2020 “Culture Decree No. PD-6000 of May 23 [3], 2020 “On measures to further enhance the role and influence of the arts in society” Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 325 of June 9, 2021 and “Marturs’ Memory” Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 357 of February 2, 2022 “On support of the Moat Fund” The normative legal acts adopted, such as Resolution No. PD – 12 of the President of the Republic of Kazakhstan [4] are becoming increasingly important.

The repertoire is the sum total of plays and solo works performed in the theater. Choosing a repertoire means finding a suitable piece to perform. When choosing a repertoire for working with students and learners, all attention should be focused on a systematic, regular learning process. For this, it is necessary to observe the direction of the work from simple to complex, from easy to difficult, and consistency in this direction.

Accordingly, when working on the word, the following steps must be taken:

1. Landscape.
2. A less eventful passage.
3. A fragment with many events.
4. Fragments of different genres.
5. Complete works or complex pieces.

The landscape belongs to the early period of the executive activity, and it makes it easier for the student to educate such features as naturalness, vision, behavior. The landscape must be selected from the work of a writer.

Also, the selected scene should be an image of a place, thing or similar object that can be clearly visualized (imagined). It should not contain sad events, terrible events or confusing thoughts. It should be simple, simple, if possible, a bright scene told by someone. The selected passage must be written in prose. There is also a tradition that even if the piece is short, it is of great importance that it is complete, that it is limited to the description of a specific object or event.

It is useful that the selected pieces of scenery should be as interesting as possible, encouraging or sparking the emotions of the student-performer. Also, with the intention of teaching the student-performer the ability to hear music and truly live under the beats (measure) of music, it is also possible to choose scenes that allow adding melodies and songs later. Also, depending on the personal characteristics, character and aspirations of students-performers, it is necessary to refer to pictorial (landscape) fragments of different authors, genres, periods and sizes. A less eventful passage. After the stage of scenery is well mastered, that is, after students master the necessary elements such as seeing and handling, the task can be made a little more difficult. If the scenes were uneventful, there may be one or two incidents that are not confusing or troublesome in the extract. It will be even better if the selected piece starts with a scene and then goes to the story.

But it is necessary to ensure that it is free from confusing events and deep psychological tasks. For the time being, passages that educate the elements of clear and clear pronunciation, strong breath, sonorous voice, good manners and vision, as well as reaction to simple events that are happening are considered. Their size (between 1.5-3 pages in the size of a notebook's handwriting) can be as follows. Dargah. A cool, pleasant morning breeze pulls the soft curtains of the open window. I raise my head from the pillow and look at the morning twilight through the window. And my heart turns. [5] At the foot of the wide yard, the raikhans are lined up in

an orderly manner. In the next rows, delicate, multi-colored ivy flowers are gently swaying. Behind the flowers are branching apple trees.

Especially the red fruiting branches of Namangan apple are shaking. Basil and apples mixed together and filled him, the courtyard, and the whole world with good deeds. Fragments with many events. Now the reader should be able to open the subtexts (the content of the text) in a conscious process, perform the set actions, and subordinate the secondary elements in the passage to the main purpose. Fragments of various genres. This section does not deny the types of genres from the previous stages, of course. But at this stage, the main focus is on students' feeling of genres, each genre and even the types of genres (for example, there is a big difference between the comedies of Erkin Vakhidov and the comedies of Said Ahmad, but both are related to the same genre - comedy) It is necessary to strive to cultivate the ability to find the right "key" now, as soon as they get hold of a work or piece, they should be able to start thinking about all its aspects and analyze it. Therefore, at this stage, it is possible to start working on 2-3 pieces of different genres at the same time.

Complete works or complex fragments. In the final stages of the educational process, the student will have to work on a piece of work or pieces with a complex plot and many events, which he has chosen according to his own taste and prepared for work by editing. During this period, it is necessary to pay attention to the creation of more mature and full-fledged images, to achieve the student's completely organic path. If the student is talented, it is possible to work on large works and even literary compositions with some of them, which will become a performance repertoire. So, when choosing a repertoire for the regular training period, the main attention should be focused on educating students about the naturalness and real life of art. Repertoire, as mentioned, should be chosen in the direction from simple to complex, from easy to difficult.

In cases that are not related to regular reading and learning, you should pay attention to the following features of repertoire selection:

1. It is necessary to ensure the diversity of the repertoire for solo performers. The listeners should always enjoy ideologically sound, impressive and valuable examples of world literature. This thing, in addition to the goal set before the performer, cultivates a taste for literature and art in them.
2. When choosing a repertoire for anniversaries, holidays and similar ceremonies, the main focus should be on choosing a theme. In such cases, one should not deviate from the topic of the ceremony. Of course, this does not mean that on the anniversary of the writer Said Ahmad, perform only the works of Said Ahmad, or on the New Year's Eve, perform only the works about the New Year. [6] However, everything should be in accordance with the theme and spirit of the ceremony. In conclusion, it should be noted that the value of the work chosen for performance is measured by its ideological superiority and artistic maturity. Such works can always attract the listener's attention and benefit them. Therefore, the repertoire chosen for speech art should be ideologically thorough, artistically mature, and convenient for mastering the basics of art. The basic repertoire should be national literature (because it will be close and familiar to the student in every way), world classical art and progressive literature can also be used appropriately and effectively.

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